

Research Article

Assessment of entrepreneurial skills required for self-employment in agriculture in colleges of education In Northwest Nigeria

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Abstract

The study assessed entrepreneurial skills required for self-employment in agriculture in colleges of education in northwest Nigeria. Two specific objectives, two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was used. The population of the study was 276 which comprised of 255 lecturers and 51 technologists. Census sampling technique was used to arrive at 244 as sample size with 198 lecturers and 46 technologists. Structure questionnaire on 5-point rating scale was developed. A reliability coefficient of 0.70 and 0.77 were obtained using Cronbach alpha coefficient reliability tool. Weighted mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while ANOVA was used to test the null hypotheses at 5% level of significant. The result revealed that all the entrepreneurial skills were for self-employment in agriculture. On the levels of agripreneurial skills assessed, 3 were found to be very highly required, fifteen were highly required and two were required. The result of the hypotheses revealed that there was no significant ($p>0.05$) difference in the mean responses of lecturers and technologists in Federal and State Colleges of Education on entrepreneurial skills for self-employment in agriculture. Also, there was no significant difference on the levels of agripreneurial skills required for self-employment in agriculture. Based on the findings, it was recommended that, the management of the Colleges of Education should send lectures and technologists for training on the area of entrepreneurial skills to better prepare students for self-employment in agriculture after graduation among others.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial skills, Agripreneurial skills, Self-employment, Agricultural Education

1. Introduction

In Nigeria agriculture is one of the major sector that boost economic growth and development by providing employment, raw materials for industries and food for the growing population. The Northwest Nigeria is largely characterized by agrarian communities where agriculture is inevitable for survival. With the increasing unemployment and underemployment, there is a critical need to reposition agriculture through entrepreneurial skills for self-employment.

Entrepreneurial skills are all about the acquisition of skills that will culminate to an individual becoming self-employed, self-reliant and then create job and wealth for himself. It involves the acquisition of skills, knowledge and competencies that will enable learners to maximize the use of existing resources for firm career commitments such as

setting up businesses, marketing service or being produce employees of organizations (Wilfred-Bonse and Sam-Ngwu 2014). Allen (2020) defined entrepreneurial skill as the ability to create something new with value by devoting the necessary time and effort associated with financial, psychic, and social risk and receiving the resultant reward and personal satisfaction and independence. Entrepreneurial skills provide entrepreneurs with learning experiences needed to enhance their individual contribution to their entrepreneurial goals. Some of the entrepreneurial skills very much needed by the entrepreneurs and are expected to be possessed by teachers so that they can successfully teach students. These include; business management skills, marketing skills, accounting skills, financial management skills, communication skills, human relations skills, ICT

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skills, risk management skills, decision-making skills, problem-solving skills, employability skills, high productivity skills, among others (Oduma 2012). Sumarnom *et al.* (2023) classified entrepreneurial skills based on the categories of basic skills as (1) conceptual skills (2) creative skills (3) managing skills, (4) communication and interaction skills and (5) skills to develop striving techniques. The acquisition of these entrepreneurial skills enables one to discover and evaluate business opportunities, gather the necessary resources, initiate appropriate actions to ensure success and implement actions to take advantage of the opportunities for rewarding outcome (Ukozor and Amaechi, 2021).

Okoli, *et al.* (2018) observed that entrepreneurial skills are competency-based resourceful skills that are capable of making an individual self-reliant, independent and productive in meeting life's challenges. They went ahead to state that possession of entrepreneurial skills makes an individual to exploit a business opportunity, establish an enterprise and run it successfully. They equally classify some of the entrepreneurial skills as, Technological skills, Resource Utilization and Management Skills, Marketing Skills, Strategic planning skills and Capability skills. Ngbongha and Akaa (2020) pointed out that entrepreneurial skills could encompass a broad range of various skills sets like technical skills, leadership and business management skills and creative thinking. These entrepreneurial skills can be applied to many different job roles and industries, developing your entrepreneurial skills can mean developing several types of skills sets. For example, to be successful in poultry you may need to develop your production and marketing skills. To build and maintain successful project teams you might need to improve your leadership and communication skills.

Self-employment refers to the situation where an individual create and takes control of a business decision. Self-employment according to Jean (2018) is a situation where an individual is the owner of a business; such individual earns a living by working for himself/herself and not as an employee of someone. This implies that self-employment is the situation of earning income directly from one's own business, trade or profession rather than as a specified salary or wages from an employer. Anaele *et al.* (2014) defined self-employment as a situation where an individual creates, begins and takes control of the business decision rather than working for an employer. Abdulkarim (2012) defined self-employment as working for oneself. He further stated that self-employment is broadly divided into two categories; the self-employed without employees and self-employed with employees. The self-employed without employees is termed a one-man business. On the other hand, self-employed with employees are the small and medium sized companies. They contribute immensely towards the

reduction of employment. To equip students with the necessary skills, knowledge and attitude for self-employment adequate facilities for teaching and learning entrepreneurial skills in agriculture must be available and put to use.

Colleges of education are one of the arms of tertiary institutions in Nigeria with the responsibility of training teachers that will function effectively at the Nursery, Primary and Junior Secondary school levels. The National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) supervises the activities of all Colleges of Education in Nigeria. The commission was established under the enabling Decree (Now Act) No 13 of 17th January 1989 (NCCE, 2017). In 2006, Federal Government directed Colleges of Education through the Federal Ministry of Education (FME) to incorporate Entrepreneurship Education into their programme with effect from 2007/2008 academic session.

The entrepreneurship education is to be offered by every student regardless of their field of specialization. The objective is to stimulate students' interest in entrepreneurship and effectively impact the knowledge, skills and attitude relevant for successful venture creation and sustenance. It is expected that every graduate in agricultural education at College of Education level apart from teaching skills and competency should acquire entrepreneurial skills to enable him/her handle and operate agricultural business using creative thinking and innovative mind-set for self-employment. The entrepreneurial aspect of agricultural education remains marginal in most colleges leading to a mismatch between what is taught and what is required for self-employment. Student graduate with limited hand-on experience, low confidence in agricultural ventures and a weak entrepreneurial mind-set. This has contributed to the increasing rate of unemployment among graduates of colleges of education, many of whom lack the skills and motivation to start their own agribusinesses.

Despite the vast agricultural potentials in the Northwest region of Nigeria and the need to curb unemployment, graduates of Colleges of Education within the zone remain largely ill equipped to pursue self-employment in agriculture. As it has been observed by many stakeholders, that most of the Colleges of Education depend more on theoretical knowledge, lacking the practical and entrepreneurial components necessary to foster self-reliance and create job among students. Hence, students lack the skills, confidence and motivation to engage in agribusiness ventures. Thereby, not contributing to economic empowerment and sustainable development in Nigeria. There is urgent need to assess the entrepreneurial skills currently being acquired in the agricultural programme of Colleges of Education in Nigeria to bridge the gap with evidence-based recommendations for enhancing self-employment outcomes among graduates.

The main objective of the study was to determine the entrepreneurial skills required for self-employment in

agriculture in Colleges of Education in Northwest Nigeria.

The specific objectives of the study were to:

- (i) examine the entrepreneurial skills for self-employment in agriculture in Colleges of Education in Northwest Nigeria
- (ii) determine the levels of agripreneurial skills required for self-employment in agriculture in Colleges of Education in Northwest Nigeria

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the entrepreneurial skills for self-employment in agriculture in Colleges of Education in Northwest Nigeria?
2. What are the levels of agripreneurial skills required for self-employment in agriculture in Colleges of Education in Northwest Nigeria?

To make valid inferences, the following null hypotheses were made and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers and technologists in Federal and State Colleges of Education on the entrepreneurial skills for self-employment in agriculture.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers and technologists in Federal and State Colleges of Education on the levels of agripreneurial skills required for self-employment in agriculture.

2. Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was used in this study. The study was conducted in Northwest Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. It is one of the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria representing both a geographical and political region of the country's Northwest. The zone is made up of seven States namely Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Sokoto and Zamfara States. The population of the study was 276, which comprised of 225 lecturers and 51 technologists of Agricultural Education Department. Census sampling technique was used because the population is manageable for the study. The sample size used for the study was 244, comprised of 198 lecturers and 46 technologists from the public Colleges of Education within the study zone. This gave rise to 88% and 90% of returns for lecturers and technologists respectively.

The researchers constructed a questionnaire named: Questionnaire for Assessing Entrepreneurial Skills Required for Self-employment in Agriculture (QAESRSA). The questionnaire was structured into sections on five-point response scale. Section A assessed entrepreneurial skills for self-employment in agriculture with 21 items on the scale of

Strongly Agree (SA) = 5, Agree (A) = 4, Undecided (UD) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1. Section B determined the levels of agripreneurial skills required for self-employment with 20 items having the response scale of Very Highly Required (VHR) = 5, Highly Required (HR) = 4, Required (R) = 3, Occasional Required (OC) = 2 and Not Required (NR) = 1. The instrument was subjected to face and content validity by three experts in which two were from the Department of Vocational Education, Ahmad Bello University, Zaria and one from the Department of Agricultural Education, Federal College of Education, Zaria.

The reliability of the instrument was established through trial testing with 15 lecturers and technologists in Adamawa State College of Education Hong, which is outside the study area. Data collected was subjected to analyses using Cronbach Alpha Coefficient reliability tool. The Cronbach alpha coefficient value were 0.70 and 0.77. The researchers with the help of one research assistant from each institution administered the instrument. The research assistant is a teaching staff in Agricultural Education programme of the institution, he was engaged in the distribution and collection of the questionnaire to ensure high rate of return.

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyse the data collected. weighted mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The following limit of numbers was used to interpret the mean value on each item on the questionnaire for specific purpose one, as 1.00 – 2.99 = Disagreed and 3.00 – 5.00 = Agreed. While for specific purpose two as 0.01 – 1.49 = Not Required 1.50 – 2.49 = Slightly Required, 2.50 – 3.49 = Required, 3.50 – 4.49 = Highly Required and 4.50 – 5.00 = Very Highly Required, as the case may be. For ANOVA, where the significant P value is greater than 0.05 level of significant, the null hypotheses was accepted and conclude that there is no significant difference between the mean responses. However, if otherwise that is significant P value is less than 0.05 level of significant the null hypotheses was rejected and conclude that there is significant difference among the mean responses.

3. Results

Responses obtained from the questionnaire were analysed and the results are presented in this section.

3.1. Answers to Research Questions

3.1.1. Research Question 1

Research Question 1: *What are the entrepreneurial skills for self-employment in agriculture in Colleges of Education in Northwest Nigeria?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on Entrepreneurial Skills for Self-employment in Agriculture

S/No.	Skills	Lecturers (n=198)		Technologists (n=46)		GPX	SD	RMK
		MEAN	SD	MEAN	SD			
1	Business development skills	4.351	0.031	4.451	0.043	4.402	0.037	A
2	Business evaluation skills	4.177	0.033	4.272	0.044	4.224	0.039	A
3	Marketing skills	4.419	0.029	4.397	0.042	4.408	0.035	A
4	Customer orientation skills	4.318	0.029	4.402	0.039	4.360	0.034	A
5	Skills to realize business opportunities	4.394	0.029	4.467	0.042	4.431	0.035	A
6	Risk management skills	4.116	0.034	4.201	0.047	4.159	0.041	A
7	Innovation skill	4.278	0.031	4.288	0.044	4.283	0.038	A
8	Monitoring skill	4.172	0.031	4.266	0.043	4.219	0.037	A
9	Decision making skill	4.500	0.027	4.582	0.038	4.541	0.032	A
10	Communication skill	4.611	0.026	4.690	0.038	4.651	0.032	A
11	Planning skill	4.591	0.027	4.603	0.038	4.597	0.033	A
12	Leadership skill	4.121	0.030	4.288	0.040	4.205	0.035	A
13	Sales skills	4.626	0.027	4.625	0.038	4.626	0.032	A
14	Critical and creative thinking skills	4.389	0.027	4.489	0.037	4.439	0.032	A
15	Branding skill	4.399	0.030	4.380	0.041	4.390	0.036	A
16	Networking skill	4.283	0.029	4.402	0.041	4.343	0.035	A
17	Teamwork skill	4.177	0.030	4.435	0.042	4.306	0.036	A
18	Time management skill	4.389	0.027	4.484	0.038	4.436	0.032	A
19	Stress management skill	4.126	0.030	4.255	0.045	4.191	0.038	A
20	Problem-solving skill	4.586	0.027	4.516	0.037	4.551	0.032	A
21	Financial skill	4.707	0.028	4.739	0.040	4.723	0.034	A
GDX, GSD						4.404	0.035	

Key: n = Number of respondents, SD = Standard Deviation, GPX = Group Mean, GDX = Grand Mean, GSD = Grand Standard Deviation, RMK = Remark, A = Agreed

The result presented on Table 1 shows that the respondents agreed that all the items are entrepreneurial skills for self-employment in agriculture with a group mean ranged from 4.159 to 4.723 with a standard deviation of 0.041 and 0.034 respectively. The grand mean of 4.404 and grand standard deviation of 0.035 shows that the responses of the respondents are close to one another and the mean.

This implies that all the respondents agreed that the 21 identified items are entrepreneurial skills for self-employment in agriculture.

3.1.2. Research Question 2

Research Question 2: *What are the levels of agripreneurial skills required for self-employment in agriculture in Colleges of Education, Northwest Nigeria?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on Agripreneurial Skills Required for Self-employment

S/N	Agripreneurial Skills	Lecturers (n=198)		Technologists (n=46)		GPX	SD	RMK
		MEAN	SD	MEAN	SD			
1	Animal nutrition	4.182	0.027	4.245	0.038	4.213	0.033	HR
2	Nursery preparation	3.879	0.026	4.250	0.034	4.064	0.030	HR
3	Raising of poultry birds	4.475	0.029	4.576	0.042	4.525	0.036	VHR
4	Proper disease management	3.955	0.024	4.288	0.034	4.121	0.029	HR
5	Fish production	4.611	0.029	4.707	0.043	4.659	0.036	VHR
6	Olericulture	3.672	0.025	3.734	0.035	3.703	0.030	HR
7	Horticulture	3.758	0.022	3.859	0.034	3.808	0.028	HR
8	Vaccination of animals	3.576	0.026	3.864	0.034	3.720	0.030	HR
9	Artificial insemination	3.303	0.024	3.554	0.034	3.429	0.029	R
10	Planting of crops	3.758	0.030	4.011	0.042	3.884	0.036	HR
11	Record keeping accuracy	4.177	0.025	4.364	0.041	4.270	0.033	HR
12	Processing, preservation and storage of produce	4.611	0.030	4.668	0.043	4.640	0.036	VHR
13	Marketing of agricultural produce	4.399	0.026	4.582	0.039	4.490	0.033	HR
14	Risk management	3.747	0.027	4.054	0.038	3.901	0.033	HR
15	Ability to prepare financial statement	4.293	0.024	4.533	0.036	4.413	0.030	HR
16	Ruminant animal management	4.136	0.028	4.299	0.042	4.218	0.035	HR
17	Bee keeping	4.167	0.024	4.255	0.035	4.211	0.030	HR
18	Snail rearing	3.202	0.028	3.326	0.045	3.264	0.036	R
19	Non-ruminant animal management	4.167	0.027	4.283	0.039	4.225	0.033	HR
20	Writing of agricultural business plan for fund	4.157	0.029	4.245	0.042	4.201	0.036	HR
GDX, GSD						4.098	0.033	

Key: n = Number of respondents, SD = Standard Deviation, GPX = Group Mean, GDX Grand Mean, GSD = Grand Standard Deviation, RMKS = Remarks, VHR = Very Highly Require, HR = Highly Required, R = Required.

The result on Table 2 shows the level of agripreneurial skill required for self-employment in agriculture. Of the 20 agripreneurial skills 3 were very highly required which include; fish production, processing, preservation and storage and raising of poultry birds with the group mean of 4.659, 4.640 and 4.523 respectively. With a standard deviation of 0.036 each. The result also revealed that 15 of the agripreneurial skills were highly required, some of which are marketing of agricultural produce, ability to prepare financial statement, non-ruminant management, animal nutrition and bee keeping with the mean of 4.490, 4.413, 4.225, 4.213 and 4.211 with standard deviation of 0.033, 0.030, 0.033, 0.033 and 0.030 respectively. The result further shows that 2 of the agripreneurial skills were required which are artificial insemination and snail rearing with a group mean of 3.429

and 3.264 and standard deviation of 0.029 and 0.036 respectively. The grand mean of 4.098 with a standard deviation of 0.033 was recorded. This standard deviation shows that the responses clustered around the mean. The grand mean implies that the agripreneurial skills were highly required.

3.2. Test of Research Hypotheses

3.2.1. Hypothesis 1

H_{01} : There is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers and technologist in Federal and State Colleges of Education on the entrepreneurial skills for self-employment in agriculture.

Table 3: ANOVA on Entrepreneurial Skills for Self-employment in Agriculture

Source of variance	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F ratio	Sig.
Between Groups	0.139	3	0.046	1.573	0.202
Within Groups	2.365	80	0.030		
Total	2.504	83			

The result on Table 3 shows an F ratio of 1.573 with a P value of 0,202, degree of freedom 3, 80 on means of the items. That is $F(3, 80) 1.573 P > 0.05$. Hence, there is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers and technologist in Federal and State Colleges of Education on entrepreneurial skills for self-employment in agriculture. Since there is no significant difference on the mean responses, the null hypothesis was upheld. This indicated

that the entrepreneurial skills are geared towards self-employment in agriculture.

3.2.2. Hypothesis 2

H_{02} : There is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers and technologist in Federal and State Colleges of Education on the levels of agripreneurial skills required for self-employment in agriculture.

Table 4: ANOVA on the Levels of Agripreneurial Skills Required for Self-employment in Agriculture

Source of variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F ratio	Sig.
Between Groups	0.616	3	0.205	1.383	0.254
Within Groups	11.283	76	0.148		
Total	11.899	79			

Result on Table 4 revealed an F ratio of 1.383 with a P value of 0.254, degree of freedom 3, 76 on means of the items. That is $F(3, 76) 1.383 P > 0.05$. Hence, there is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers and technologist in Federal and State Colleges of Education on the levels of agripreneurial skills required for self-employment in agriculture. Since there is no significant difference in the mean responses, the null hypothesis was upheld. This indicated that the agripreneurial skills are required for self-employment in agriculture.

successfully. These skills items agreed with the submission of Oduma (2012) as business management skills, marketing skills, accounting skills, financial management skills, communication skills, risk management skills, decision-making skills, and problem-solving skills among others. The nature and quality of the skills an entrepreneur posse invariably defines the future and successfulness of the business. As noted by Jing and Alison (2020) entrepreneurial skills that guarantees business success include, creative thinking and innovation risk management, leadership and communication skills. These skills make an entrepreneur and the business thick, strong and viable. The acquisition of these entrepreneurial skills will enable agricultural education graduates to find and evaluate business opportunities, gather the necessary resources, initiate appropriate action to ensure success and implement action to take advantage of the opportunities in agriculture for rewarding outcome. As Okoli

4. Discussion

The findings revealed that all the 21 entrepreneurial skills are needed for self-employment in agriculture in Colleges of Education. This implies that these skills are necessary to enable agricultural education graduate start, develop, sustain and finance an enterprise in agriculture

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et al. (2018) affirmed that entrepreneurial skills are competency based resourceful skills that are capable of making individual self-reliant, independent and productive in meeting life challenges. On the other hand, Tarhan (2021) in his study on entrepreneurial skills in the context of teaching programme in Poland included ability to guess, need analysis skills, ability to detect product quality and advertising skills.

However, Ngbongha and Akaa (2020) reported that entrepreneurial skills could encompass a broad range of various skills set like technical skills, leadership and business management skills and creative thinking. Because entrepreneurial skills can be applied to many different job roles and industries, developing your entrepreneurial skills can mean developing several types of skills set. For example, to be successful in poultry production you need to develop your production and marketing skills. To build and maintain successful project teams you might need to improve your leadership and communication skills. Charney and Libecap (2015) stated that graduates who acquire entrepreneurial skills were on average three times more likely to be involved in the creation of a new business than non-entrepreneurial skills cohort was.

The findings also revealed that all the agripreneurial skills were highly required for self-employment in agriculture in Colleges of Education as indicated by the grand mean. However, fish production, processing, preservation and storage of produce and raising of poultry birds are very highly required. Marketing of agricultural produce, ability to prepare financial statement, non-ruminant animal management, animal nutrition, bee keeping among others are highly required while artificial insemination and snail rearing are required. This could be attributed to the demand and preference within the area of study. For instance, snail is not commonly consume within the study area. This result agreed with Olaniyi et al. (2020) who studied the perceived agripreneurail skills needs of undergraduate's students in university of Ibadan and identified writing of agricultural business plan, customers' relation skills, marketing of agricultural produce ability to prepare financial statement among others. In the same vain this result agreed with that of Emeh and Edin (2019) who reported that animal production skills, disease management skills, crop production skills, communication skills, managerial skills and marketing skills were required by students of agricultural education for self-employment in Ebony State. This result implies that the myriad of agripreneurial skills portend avalanche of opportunities for choice making for graduate of Agricultural Education to identify at least one area and venture into as agripreneurial skills are numerous entrepreneurship activities related to agriculture. The agricultural sector both public and private requires skilled individuals who are capable to deal with all aspects of work in agriculture. Skilled workers would be able to increase production, qualitative and quantitatively

The result of ANOVA on entrepreneurial skills for self-

employment in agriculture shows that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers and technologists in Federal and State Colleges of Education. Since, there is no significant difference on the mean responses the null hypothesis was upheld. The result implies that both lecturers and technologists in Federal and State Colleges of Education generally agreed that the identified entrepreneurial skills are geared towards self-employment in agriculture. That is they are requirement for self-employment in agriculture. For instance, Ezeani (2014) reported that without marketing skills, entrepreneurs' chances of remaining in business is very slim. Anaele et al. (2014) also reported that, these skills stabilize and give confidence to the entrepreneur.

On the agripreneurial skills required for self-employment in agriculture the ANOVA shows that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers and technologists in Federal and State Colleges of Education. This implies that the null hypothesis of no significant difference was upheld. This indicated that both lecturers and technologist in Federal and State Colleges of Education agreed that the agripreneurial skills are highly required for self-employment in agriculture. The result is supported by, Emeh and Edwin (2019) whose findings show no significant difference in the mean responses of entrepreneurs and lecturers on skills required by agricultural education students for self-employment in Ebonyi State. This implies that in order to prepare agricultural education students to acquire the required skills, knowledge and attitude for successful business career in agriculture emphasis should focused on fish production skills, processing, preservation and storage, raising of poultry birds, marketing of agricultural produce, ability to prepare financial report among other. However, Abiodun et al. (2015) observed that students only struggle hard to obtained certificate rather than the knowledge and skills that would make them self-employed.

5. Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study Agricultural Education Students in Colleges of Education in Northwest Nigeria need entrepreneurial skills such as business management skills, marketing skills, accounting skills, financial management skills, communication skills, human relations skills, ICT skills, risk management skills, decision-making skills, problem-solving skills, employability skills, high productivity skills, among others for self-employment after graduation.

Recommendations:

Based on the findings the following recommendations were made:

- The management of the Colleges of Education should send lecturers and technologists for training on the area of entrepreneurial skills to better prepare students for self-employment after graduation.

- Federal government should make provision for granting single digit interest loan to Agricultural Education students' graduates to establish an agricultural enterprise of their choice after graduation.
- All stakeholders in this sector of education should put more effort in improving the teaching and learning of entrepreneurial skills for self-employment in agriculture.
- The department in collaboration with the school management should collaborate with firms, non-governmental organizations and donor agencies for the improvement of teaching and learning of entrepreneurial skills development of students for self-employment in agriculture.

Abbreviations

QAESRSA	Questionnaire for Assessing Entrepreneurial Skills Required for Self-employment in Agriculture
NCCE	National Commission for Colleges of Education
GSD	Grand Standard Deviation
SD	Standard Deviation
GPX	Group Mean

Author Contributions

Joshua, Yusuf Fachano: Conceptualization, Methodology, writing- original draft,

Titus James: Methodology, Analysis of result,

Abubakar Bayero: Writing-Review and Editing

Conflicts of Interest

The author(s) declare that they have no known competing financial interests, professional affiliations or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper,

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